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Using behavioural insights to increase older adults' acceptance of camera-based active and assisted living technologies: An experimental medicine approach

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Abstract

Camera-based active and assisted living (AAL) technologies are a transformative solution to the challenges of population ageing but are hardly accepted by older adults. Few solutions have been offered to combat this issue of non-acceptance. The present research therefore employs behaviour change theory, couched in an experimental medicine approach, in an attempt to uncover strategies to increase older adults' acceptance of said technology. Results shed light on a fruitful target for interventions aimed at increasing said acceptance: future self-continuity – that is, individuals' sense of connectedness to their future self. Further insights are provided on novel means of targeting future self-continuity within acceptance-enhancing interventions.

Introduction

Many decisions involve making trade-offs between outcomes that arise in the present and those that attain in the future – these decisions are known as intertemporal decisions (Frederick et al., 2002). Intertemporal decisions are typically characterised by making small immediate sacrifices (e.g., foregoing dietary indulgences) for larger gains in the future (e.g., maintaining a healthy weight; Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009; Rutchick et al., 2018). The decision to accept or reject camera-based active and assisted living (AAL) technologies is one such example. This is because the use of camera-based AAL technologies involves enduring upfront costs such as privacy violations (Mihailidis et al., 2008) and the stigmatising identity of being in receipt of assistance (Faucett et al., 2017). By contrast, the benefits of using the technology including improved health, safety, independence, wellbeing, and longevity, typically only manifest in the future (van den Broek et al., 2010). The decision to accept and use camera-based AAL technologies can thus be understood as an intertemporal one, requiring that older adults make costly immediate sacrifices in service of their long-run interests.

A remarkably frequent behavioural phenomenon is that when confronting intertemporal choice scenarios, people tend towards immediately gratification at the expense of larger future gains – a phenomenon known as temporal discounting (Fuchs, 1982; Lynch & Zauberman, 2006). In brief, people tend to discount the value of future gains, preferring instead to maximise immediate outcomes for themselves (Chapman & Elstein, 1995). From failing to save enough for retirement to neglecting healthy dietary practice, examples of temporal discounting abound in everyday life (Thaler & Benartzi, 2004).

An emerging line of research suggests that temporal discounting arises due to an inability to connect and empathise with one's future self. *Future self-continuity* can be understood as the degree to which individuals feel psychologically connected to their future selves, and is often elevated where the future self is: seen as similar to their current self, vividly envisioned, and positively appraised (Bixter et al., 2020; Hershfield et al., 2009; Sokol & Serper, 2019). According to a future self-continuity hypothesis, just as individuals have little reason to save resources for strangers to whom they do not feel connected, so too do they have little rational motive to reward their future self (Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009; Hershfield, 2011; Hershfield et al., 2009). In line with this theorising, there is an extensive literature documenting the influence of future self-*discontinuity* on non-adaptive, impatient behaviour. For example, feeling dissimilar to the future self has shown associations with low retirement savings rates (Ersner-Hershfield et al., 2009) and low levels of physical activity (Rutchick et al., 2018), while individuals who report less (versus more) vivid imageries of their future selves tend to eat less healthily (Dalley, 2016) and save less for retirement (Ellen et al., 2012; Hershfield et al., 2011).

Discontinuity to the future self may reasonably account for older adults' disinclination towards camera-based AAL technologies. This is because if the above theorising holds that the use of said technology can be construed as an immediately costly action taken in service of future interests – that is, in service of the *future self's* interests – then older adults who feel disconnected to their future selves may be unwilling to take such costly action in present day.

Research Aim

Despite frequent and growing reports on older adults' poor acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies, few strategies have been devised to augment this acceptance. This programme of research therefore set out to explore, identify, and target within an intervention a hypothesised psychological barrier to older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies – future self-continuity – with a view to increasing the acceptance of said technology.

Methods

The experimental medicine approach, which advocates a theory-led, mechanisms focused approach to changing behaviour (Nielsen et al., 2018; Sheeran et al., 2017), was used as the research approach. The experimental medicine approach to behaviour change comprises four key steps: (i) to identify potentially malleable factors that can be targeted in an intervention to change behaviour; (ii) to validate the target by identifying measures of the target and examining whether changes in the target are associated with changes in the behavioural outcome of interest; (iii) to engage the target through experimental manipulation; and (iv) to conduct a full test of the proposed behaviour change model by investigating whether an intervention that contains those manipulations leads to change in the behavioural outcome of interest, and whether this change is mediated (i.e., explained by) changes in the target (Nielsen et al., 2018). Here, future self-continuity is the candidate target of focus within the programme of research.

Four key research activities were undertaken in line with the experimental medicine approach, with a view to increasing older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. First, a scoping review was conducted to identify the barriers and facilitators to older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies that span important physical, environmental, social, and psychological domains. Second, a cross-sectional study was conducted to examine the association between an identified target (i.e., future self-continuity) and acceptance. Thereafter, qualitative work was undertaken to adapt and optimise a so-called “future-self intervention” designed to increase older adults' future self-

continuity. Finally, an online randomised experimental study was examined the effect of the developed future-self intervention on acceptance.

Results

A scoping review identified 47 barriers and facilitators to older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies. Barriers included privacy concerns surrounding the technology, distaste for the technology's stigmatising quality, and skepticism about the technology's potential to displace cherished forms of human mediated care. Facilitators included the perceived usefulness of the technology for improving safety, independence, and overall wellbeing, older adults' perceived need for the technology, and assurance of data security. Of these, a particular barrier – i.e., the tendency to defer one's need for the technology into the future and onto other people – was the theoretical basis on which future self-continuity was identified as a putative candidate target for an acceptance-facilitating intervention.

A subsequent cross-sectional study ($n = 183$) revealed significant associations between future self-continuity and acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies among older adults. Specifically, older adults who reported experiencing their future selves in more vivid (odds ratio = 3.21, 95% CI [1.94, 5.31], $p < .001$) or positive (odds ratio = 3.09, 95% CI [1.76, 5.43], $p < .001$) terms were significantly more likely to say that they would install the technology in their homes today. This result justified the subsequent research activity, where semi-structured interviews with $n = 7$ older adults yielded a “future-self intervention” that was optimally usable, acceptable, relevant, and feasible for use with older adults. The intervention was evaluated in an online randomised controlled study ($n = 181$), which revealed a significant positive effect of the intervention on acceptance but only among those aged 64 years and below ($B = .121$, $SE = .057$, $p = .037$) – an effect mediated by felt positivity to the future self ($B = .047$, 95% CI [.005, .126]). No acceptance-facilitating effect of the intervention was found for those aged 65 and above ($B = -.089$, $SE = .058$, $p = .122$).

Discussion

In adopting an experimental medicine approach to behavior change, the present research isolated a novel psychological target for interventions aimed at increasing older adults' acceptance of camera-based AAL technologies – i.e., future self-continuity. Results stand to inform the development of acceptance-facilitating interventions, as they suggest that intervention strategies that increase older adults' felt connection to their future self – and in particular, those which increase the positivity with which future selves are appraised – should have beneficial effects on the acceptance of said technology.

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References

- Bixter, M. T., McMichael, S. L., Bunker, C. J., Adelman, R. M., Okun, M. A., Grimm, K. J., Graudejus, O., & Kwan, V. S. Y. (2020). A test of a triadic conceptualization of future self-identification. *PLOS ONE*, 15(11), pp. e0242504.
- Cardinaux, F., Bhowmik, D., Abhayaratne, C., & Hawley, M. S. (2011). Video based technology for ambient assisted living: A review of the literature. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Smart Environments*, 3(3), pp. 253–269.
- Chapman, G. B., & Elstein, A. S. (1995). Valuing the future: temporal discounting of health and money. *Medical Decision Making: An International Journal of the Society for Medical Decision Making*, 15(4), pp. 373–386.
- Dalley, S. E. (2016). Does the salience of possible selves mediate the impact of approach and avoidance temperaments on women's weight-loss dieting? *Personality and Individual Differences*, 88, pp. 267–271.
- Ellen, P. S., Wiener, J. L., & Paula Fitzgerald, M. (2012). Encouraging People to save for their Future: Augmenting Current Efforts with Positive Visions of the Future. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 31(1), pp. 58–72.
- Ersner-Hershfield, H., Garton, M. T., Ballard, K., Samanez-Larkin, G. R., & Knutson, B. (2009). Don't stop thinking about tomorrow: Individual differences in future self-continuity account for saving. *Judgment and Decision Making*, 4(4), pp. 280–286.
- Faucett, H. A., Ringland, K. E., Cullen, A. L. L., & Hayes, G. R. (2017). (In)Visibility in Disability and Assistive Technology. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 10(4), pp. 1–17.
- Frederick, S., Loewenstein, G., & O'Donoghue, T. (2002). Time Discounting and Time Preference: A Critical Review. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 40(2), pp. 351–401.
- Fuchs, V. (1982). Time Preference and Health: An Exploratory Study (pp. 93-120 *BT-Economic Aspects of Health*). National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.
- Hershfield, H. E. (2011). Future self-continuity: how conceptions of the future self transform intertemporal choice. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1235(1), pp. 30–43.
- Hershfield, H. E., Goldstein, D. G., Sharpe, W. F., Fox, J., Yeykelis, L., Carstensen, L. L., & Bailenson, J. N. (2011). Increasing saving behavior through age-progressed renderings of the future self. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 48, pp. S23–S37.
- Hershfield, H. E., Wimmer, G. E., & Knutson, B. (2009). Saving for the future self: Neural measures of future self-continuity predict temporal discounting. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience*, 4(1), pp. 85–92.
- Lynch, J. G., & Zauberman, G. (2006). When do you Want It? Time, Decisions, and Public Policy. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 25(1), pp. 67–78.
- Mihailidis, A., Cockburn, A., Longley, C., & Boger, J. (2008). The acceptability of home monitoring technology among community-dwelling older adults and baby boomers. *Assistive Technology: The Official Journal of RESNA*, 20(1), pp. 1–12.

- Nielsen, L., Riddle, M., King, J. W., Aklin, W. M., Chen, W., Clark, D., Collier, E., Czajkowski, S., Esposito, L., Ferrer, R., Green, P., Hunter, C., Kehl, K., King, R., Onken, L., Simmons, J. M., Stoeckel, L., Stoney, C., Tully, L., & Weber, W. (2018). The NIH Science of Behavior Change Program: Transforming the science through a focus on mechanisms of change. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 101, pp. 3–11.
- Rutchick, A. M., Slepian, M. L., Reyes, M. O., Pleskus, L. N., & Hershfield, H. E. (2018). Future self-continuity is associated with improved health and increases exercise behavior. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Applied*, 24(1), pp. 72–80.
- Sheeran, P., Klein, W. M. P., & Rothman, A. J. (2017). Health Behavior Change: Moving from Observation to Intervention. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 68, pp. 573–600.
- Sokol, Y., & Serper, M. (2019). Development and Validation of a Future Self-Continuity Questionnaire: A Preliminary Report. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 102(5), pp. 677–688.
- Thaler, R. H., & Benartzi, S. (2004). Save more tomorrow™: Using behavioral economics to increase employee saving. *Journal of Political Economy*, 112(1), pp. S164–S187.
- van den Broek, G., Cavallo, F., & Wehrmann, C. (2010). *AALIANCE Ambient Assisted Living Roadmap*. IOS Press.